

Absa Youth Entrepreneurship Dialogue Outcomes Report

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AGCAE
Allan Gray Centre for
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Introduction

The **Absa Youth Entrepreneurship Dialogue** took place in Johannesburg on **19 February 2025** – an energetic, dynamic meeting that brought entrepreneurs, funders, policymakers, researchers, and corporate leaders together.

But the strongest voices of the day were those of the youth – and giving them a platform was the main aim of the event hosted by **Absa Group Corporate Citizenship** and the **Allan Gray Centre for Africa Entrepreneurship (AGCAE)**. The event was aligned to the **2024 AfriLabs Annual Gathering (AAG)** and its theme to unite innovation and entrepreneurial innovation across the continent. This was also informed by AAG's continental tracks, **Daniel Isenberg's ecosystem model**, and AGCAE's **Africa Entrepreneurial Ecosystem Index**.

This report captures the day's significant events - like **the formal launch of Absa's Financial Inclusion through Entrepreneurship Strategy as well as** lively discussions around support at all stages of the entrepreneurial process; co-creation in systems, policy reform as well as more peer-to-peer support and integrated community hubs, better financing models and greater access to markets. **Language emerged as a major barrier.** Also, during the day, hackathon-based policymaking was celebrated as a best practice for inclusive and agile policy development, not to mention how a successful **Start-Up Act for South Africa** should be structured.

Conceptually, the idea was to align and link the Ecosystem Dialogue to the AAG continental themes. The AAG was held on 5 to 8 November 2024, in Cape Town, South Africa, and promoted collaboration, knowledge exchange, and enhancement of transformative initiatives that can boost progress the continent.

This aligns well with Absa and AGCAE planned initiatives to drive and augment inclusive entrepreneurial ecosystems in South Africa and other parts of Africa using a data-and-dialogue driven approach. Similarly, the Absa Youth Entrepreneurship Dialogue contributes to Absa's new **Financial Inclusion through Entrepreneurship Strategy and AGCAE's ecosystem building objective.**

During the Dialogue sessions, solutions and initiatives were presented and this report shares these as well as an **Outcomes Analysis** shining a light on structural gaps and innovative opportunities. Finally, the **Conclusion emphasises the practical next steps for building inclusive, youth-responsive entrepreneurial ecosystems in South Africa and beyond.**

Event in numbers

Invitation database:

1 142 emails sent,

46.5% opened email

Registrations:

228 registrations

171 total check-ins

60.5% invitee conversion rate

Entrepreneurship exhibition:

7 entrepreneurs made

R18 840 in sales at the event

Engagement:

60% of participants said they would

take entrepreneurial action

following event

Data-and-dialogue ecosystem approach

Why this matters:

A youth-responsive entrepreneurial ecosystem cannot be built on assumptions. It needs **evidence to guide decisions** and **dialogue to co-create solutions**. Our approach includes:

Evidence as compass

The AGCAE's *Africa Entrepreneurial Ecosystem Index* and ongoing diagnostics provided a baseline of data on structural realities facing youth.

Dialogue as driver

The Dialogue was co-designed to put young entrepreneurs at the centre, bringing them into conversation with funders, corporates, educators, and policymakers.

Ecosystem as an approach

More than a one-off event, the approach contributes to Absa's *Financial Inclusion through Entrepreneurship Strategy* and AGCAE's ecosystem-building agenda.

“Entrepreneurship is not just about business ideas—it’s about building ecosystems that give young people the skills, networks, and opportunities they need to succeed.” – Youth Entrepreneurship Dialogue delegate

Support

In the session facilitated by Mr Josh Adler, Chief Programmes Officer, African Leadership Academy, and Ms Xolile Mabuza, contributor and youth entrepreneur, **the importance of investing earlier in young entrepreneurs emerged.**

Other key insights:

Evidence from the **Anzisha Prize** shows: **data-driven, youth-tested models are more effective and sustainable**

Coaching builds adaptability and resilience, better preparing youth for an unpredictable future. More effective than traditional mentorship

Support should go **beyond business skills** to include self-confidence, mental wellness, and personal growth

Start early — investing in entrepreneurs aged 15–22 has a powerful ripple effect—young founders create jobs for other young people

Entrepreneurs like Xolile Mabuza show that young people are not just recipients—they must **co-create the support systems that serve them**

Suggested ways of support, initiatives & platforms

Theme	Key Ideas	Suggested Initiatives
<p>Youth-centred coaching over traditional mentorship.</p>	<p>Traditional mentorship assumes a stable future. But the future is uncertain — and young people need agile, skills-based coaching to navigate it.</p>	<p>Fund peer-to-peer coaching among young entrepreneurs. Develop Youth Entrepreneur Coaching Academies with scalable, context-sensitive models. Train coaches in both business acumen and psychological support, including identity and resilience development.</p>
<p>Localised support for township and rural youth.</p>	<p>Young entrepreneurs, especially in underserved regions, need proximity-based support that reflects their realities.</p>	<p>Expand community-based entrepreneurial support hubs, ideally in partnership with schools, NGOs, and local leaders. Integrate non-financial support (e.g., mental wellness, identity formation) into incubator models. Embed digital inclusion, including access to tools and training, especially outside metros.</p>

Theme	Key Ideas	Suggested Initiatives
<p>Evidence-based and youth-led support models.</p>	<p>Support programmes must be informed by data—and that data must be youth-generated and youth-interpreted.</p>	<p>Create a Pan-African Youth Entrepreneurship Lab to collect and interpret impact data. Invest in research that tracks the effectiveness of different support mechanisms for young entrepreneurs aged 15–22. Partner with institutions like AGCAE to publish open-access insights for policymakers and funders.</p>
<p>Entrepreneur-led advocacy and design.</p>	<p>Support is most impactful when youth shape it themselves.</p>	<p>Institutionalise youth co-design processes in all support programme development. Fund storytelling and documentation of youth entrepreneur journeys to inform new models.</p>

“Support must help youth see themselves as entrepreneurs—before the world sees them that way.”- Youth Entrepreneurship Dialogue delegate

“You don't know the future you're mentoring the youth for.” - Youth Entrepreneurship Dialogue delegate

Polycymaking

Facilitated by Prof Isaac Khambule, Director, Africa Centre for Evidence, UJ, this session featured contributors **Ms Belinda Baah**, Co-Director, i4Policy, **Mr Bradley Thabo Mphuti**, CEO, National Youth Afrocentric Alliance (youth entrepreneur) and **Mr Colin Leshou**, Acting Group Executive: Ecosystem and Stakeholder Management, SEDFA. They highlighted the language barriers and gaps in existing policies.

Key Insights:

- South Africa's youth unemployment rate remains alarmingly high—**66% (ages 15–24)**—requiring urgent, youth-centred interventions
- Senegal's **hackathon-based policymaking** was celebrated as a best practice for inclusive and agile policy development
- A **Start-Up Act for South Africa** is in development—youth voices must shape it
- Language remains a barrier; policies like the Small Business Act should be accessible in local languages
- Entrepreneurs must be **included in policy design**, not just consulted
- **Place-based policy** is essential—different regions face different realities and regulatory needs
- **Scale requires systemic change**, not isolated interventions—policy must integrate with education, finance, and support structures

Suggested ways to address policy reform

Theme	Key Ideas	Suggested Initiatives
Policy development	Run hackathon-style development	Convene a pilot policy hackathon; explore use in Start-Up Act development.
Financial mechanisms	Experimental funding; entrepreneurship by acquisition	Launch fund allowing youth to "fail forward" and support youth business acquisition.
Ecosystem support	Tools, hubs, and regulatory ease	Conduct regulatory gap audit with input from township entrepreneurs.
Sustainability & scale	Policy must scale through national systems and integrated strategies	Align policy reform with other systems (education, finance), leverage partnerships for scale.
Inclusivity & accessibility	Accessibility in language and policy design critical to engagement	Ensure multi-language rollout of key policies (e.g. Small Business Act in Zulu, Sepedi, etc.)

“If the Small Business Act is in English, it’s not for us.”

- Youth Entrepreneurship Dialogue delegate

“Policy isn’t just a government responsibility; it’s a community dialogue.”

- Youth Entrepreneurship Dialogue delegate

Funding & markets

Perhaps one of the most enlightening sessions was led by **Ms Shiluba Mawela**, Founder & Managing Partner of Tshiamo Impact Partners. Contributors such as **Dr Jason Van Staden**, Innovative Finance Project Manager at Bertha Centre, UCT, **Mr Joseph Khoza**, founder of StritGRAD (a youth entrepreneur), and **Ms Khanya Matshikwe**, Head of Customer Value Proposition – SME at Absa, truly addressed the issue of funding for young entrepreneurs.

Their key insights:

- Funding should be seen as a **means to an end**, not the end itself
- Innovative instruments like **outcomes-based funding** and **collateral-free lending** are unlocking new opportunities for very young entrepreneurs
- Youth entrepreneurs called for **localised support**, including workshops and innovation hubs in townships and rural areas
- Funding must be coupled with **mentorship, financial literacy**, and market access
- **Access to market** is as important as access to finance. Entrepreneurs need platforms to sell, distribute, and scale offerings, especially digitally and across borders
- **Regulatory red tape and inaccessible government funding processes** were cited as major hindrances

Suggestions on how to improve funding

Theme	Key Ideas	Suggested Initiatives
Blended finance	Green Outcomes Fund, pre-funded SME credit cards, public-private partnerships	Expand outcomes-based pilots with youth-focused metrics; Absa to explore Pan-African instruments.
Flexible instruments	Forgivable loans, micro-equity, hybrid grant-loan models	Design recovery-based youth funding models that de-risk early experimentation.
Access & literacy	Financial skills integration, gamified compliance, rural workshops	Partner with education & TVET institutions for curriculum integration and township rollouts.
Ecosystem innovation	More hubs, local market linkages, 4IR tools	Launch township-based incubators and reform investment committees to include youth perspectives.
Market enablement	Need for more platforms and trade routes for youth businesses	Strengthen AfCFTA access; host regional trade showcases; invest in e-commerce integration for township SMEs.
Simplification	Bureaucracy around funding and compliance deters youth engagement	Streamline access to public/private funding and design intuitive application processes for startups.

“Funding is not the end goal—it’s the fuel to get us where we need to go.”

– Youth Entrepreneurship Dialogue delegate

“We need funds that let us fail forward, not punish us for taking risks.”

– Youth Entrepreneurship Dialogue delegate

Outcomes analysis

A few unifying themes and cross-cutting ideas emerged that point to both structural gaps and innovative opportunities for Absa and its ecosystem partners:

Theme	Insights
Youth at the centre	Young people were not passive participants—they co-facilitated sessions, contributed to Ideathon panels, and were the focus of the pop-up marketplace. Their presence was both symbolic and functional, emphasising that youth must shape , not just benefit from, ecosystem interventions.
Reflective and action-based learning	Stakeholders highlighted the importance of collective reflection —stepping back to assess existing approaches, critically examining what is and isn't working, and iterating with humility and evidence.
Entrepreneurial mindset & ecosystem building	Beyond finance or policy, mindset development —confidence, self-efficacy, and peer networks—emerged as essential. Youth entrepreneurs who hire their peers are a multiplier force for change. Ideathon leads emphasised that coaching and exposure to role models are crucial.
Policy as a scaling tool	Policy must be inclusive, multilingual, and place-based , adapting to diverse regional needs. A systemic insight was that policy enables scale when it is integrated into national systems, not when it sits in isolation from education or finance systems.

Theme	Insights
True collaboration for collective impact	Stakeholders challenged superficial collaboration. Real impact requires shared goals, standardised metrics, and continuous communication . Partnership is not just co-location—it must be intentional, resourced, and outcomes-driven.
Measuring impact beyond compliance	The dialogue identified an important gap: how to move beyond tick-box impact metrics to track long-term transformation. This includes social impact, community trust, and systems change—not just SME counts or disbursement volumes.
Digital & continental market access	A call was made to leverage digital platforms and trade frameworks like the AfCFTA to broaden access to continental markets, especially for township entrepreneurs often excluded from traditional trade and procurement networks.
Entrepreneurship as identity & inclusion	Testimonies (e.g. Xolile's) reinforced that entrepreneurship isn't just economic—it's personal. Youth felt seen and valued by Absa, strengthening the brand's social license and deepening community trust. "They see you before the business," one youth participant said.

Strategic pathways for Absa

In line with the dialogue's vision of "Fostering Collaboration, Innovation and Inclusion for Sustainable Entrepreneurial Action," the following strategic steps are proposed for Absa:

1. Reimagine support as holistic infrastructure

- Embed **entrepreneurial mindset development** into programmes through coaching, exposure, and local role models
- Scale **ecosystem-based coaching models**, particularly for those with limited networks (e.g. school leavers, rural youth)

2. Activate inclusive, systemic policy leadership

- Convene **policy hackathons** and youth-led working groups
- Champion **inclusive, multilingual legislation** (like the Small Business Act)
- Ensure national policy reforms **integrate** with Absa's entrepreneurial offerings (education, finance, digital)

3. Evolve funding into enabling instruments

- Roll out **forgivable loans, pre-funded SME cards, and micro-equity** products
- Expand **financial literacy** via gamified learning, rural workshops, and TVET partnerships
- Collaborate with funders for **ring-fenced outcome-based pilots** tied to youth metrics

4. Commit to collective impact partnerships

- Coordinate shared measurement and **long-term monitoring systems**
- Align internal teams (Strategy, Citizenship, Relationship Banking) for unified execution
- Position Absa as a **backbone organisation** supporting a youth entrepreneurship coalition

5. Seize the continental opportunity

- Explore partnerships to unlock **AfCFTA benefits** for youth-led SMEs
- Host a **Pan-African youth entrepreneur summit** to share learnings and scale solutions
- Invest in digital tools that **enable trans-border trade and access** for informal businesses

Conclusion: From dialogue to collective action

This Dialogue was a milestone in launching Absa's **Financial Inclusion through Entrepreneurship (FITE)** agenda with real youth voices at the table. It affirmed that entrepreneurship is not only about creating businesses—it's about creating **agency**, **access**, and **aspiration**

Absa has already begun building the trust and infrastructure needed to lead this movement. Now, the call is to step it up—by **institutionalising this momentum**, **scaling what works**, and **challenging what doesn't**. The **Allan Gray Centre for Africa Entrepreneurship (AGCAE)**, Absa's strategic partner in convening this Dialogue, plays a **pivotal role** in advancing this agenda. With its vision of enabling **entrepreneurship-led sustainable development** through a **data-and-dialogue-driven approach**, AGCAE provides the backbone for ecosystem intelligence and collective learning.

AGCAE's mission to integrate, create, and diffuse entrepreneurial knowledge supports Absa's goal to develop responsive, evidence-informed interventions. Its regional focus on **ecosystem diagnostics**, **policy engagement**, and **youth inclusion** ensures that ecosystem strengthening is **grounded in African realities** and **driven by African priorities**.

Together, **Absa and AGCAE** form a powerful platform for entrepreneurship as a catalyst for **intergenerational inclusion** and **socio-economic transformation**.

“Entrepreneurship is not just about business ideas—it’s about building ecosystems that provide young people with the skills, networks, and opportunities they need to succeed.”

– Youth Entrepreneurship Dialogue delegate

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